

Enslaved nobles, ennobled slaves: The inversion of Roman society in Tacitus' description of the reign of Tiberius

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Abstract

The following paper approaches Tacitus' criticism of the Roman Principate in his Annals by analyzing several key episodes from the reign of Tiberius as described by the Roman historiographer, and looking in particular at Tacitus' implied inversion of the roles of master and slave under the emperor's reign.

By taking Tiberius as an example, the paper aims to invite further research into slavery and enslavement tropes in Tacitus' later works, as well as their usage as means of denouncing the Principate as unjust. Besides Tacitus, Sallust and Suetonius serve as important sources, the first as an influence on the Annales, the second as an author who has drawn from them.

Introduction

The Roman historiographer and senator Cornelius Tacitus (~58-117 CE) witnessed an age in which the Principate had already established itself as an accepted and stable institution of the Roman *res publica*.¹ The transitions between specific principes were no longer characterized by the potential return to Republican rule, but much rather by the question which Roman noble would be the next one to lay claim to the role of autocrat. Despite the Principate having become seemingly inexorable, Tacitus is anything but flattering towards it in his writings. During the first passages of his *Annales*, he explores the origins of the Principate and identifies the

¹ Anthony R. Birley, "The Life and Death of Cornelius Tacitus," *Historia: Zeitschrift für Alte Geschichte* 49 (2000); 246-247.

increasing accumulation of important privileges and positions of power by a single person, Augustus Caesar, as the process which lays the foundation of the autocratic authority for all principes following him. It is from this point going forward that Tacitus associates the decline of Republican values with the moral decline of its formerly dominant upper class:

[...] nullo adversante, cum ferocissimi per acies aut proscriptione cecidissent, ceteri nobilium, quanto quis servitio promptior, opibus et honoribus extollerentur ac novis ex rebus aucti tuta et praesentia quam vetera et periculosa mallent. neque provinciae illum rerum statum abnuebant, suspecto senatus populique imperio ob certamina potentium et avaritiam magistratum, invalido legum auxilio quae vi ambitu postremo pecunia turbabantur.

He was wholly unopposed, for the boldest spirits had fallen in battle, or in the proscription, while the remaining nobles, the readier they were to be slaves, were raised the higher by wealth and promotion, so that, aggrandised by revolution, they preferred the safety of the present to the dangerous past. Nor did the provinces dislike that condition of affairs, for they distrusted the government of the Senate and the people, because of the rivalries between the leading men and the capacity of the officials, while the protection of the laws was unavailing, as they were continually deranged by violence, intrigue, and finally by corruption.²

It is thus already at the very beginning of his *Annales* that Tacitus characterizes the relationship between Rome's aristocracy and the *princeps* as equivalent to the relationship between slaves and their master. He provides a lens through which all following interactions between these two factions of Roman rule are to be observed in the coming chapters of his work.

William Turpin ascribes to Tacitus the intent of teaching his readership through moralizing *exempla*.³ It can be assumed then that tropes associated with slavery play a central role in these exemplary narratives, in particular with regards to the Principate.

² Tac. Ann. 1.2.1.

³ William Turpin, "Stoic exempla, and the praecipuum munus annalium," *Classical Antiquity* 27 (2008); 360.

In the following essay, the tropes and symbols of slavery from Tacitus' *Annales* with regards to the interaction between the principes and the other members of Roman society are to be analyzed on an exemplary level. With regards to the usage of similar tropes among Tacitus' influences, namely Sallust (86-34/5 BCE), the role of slavery topics in Tacitus' establishment of moral *exempla* is to be investigated. The focus of the observation is to lie on the reign of Tiberius, covered in the first six volumes of Tacitus' *Annales*, as this is the first complete reign the historiographer describes in the *Annales*, which is why many of the tropes that will be utilised in his descriptions of later *principes* make their first appearance here. A more extended analysis of the topic could cover a larger part of the *Annales*, but would go beyond the scope of this essay.

The topic of the *princeps* Tiberius as tyrant in Tacitus' works has been approached in other articles, namely by A.J. Woodman in "Tiberius and the Taste of Power" (2006), which explores the depiction of the princeps as the literal devourer of the Republic.⁴ Rebecca Edwards has discussed Tiberius' retreat to Capri, a passage of Tacitus in which many exhibitions of tyrannical or enslaving behaviour, including the fragmentary *coprea*-episode mentioned below,⁵ are shown, pointing out how the island's superficial charm and deep-lying corruption mirrors its most prominent inhabitant.⁶ The topic of Tiberius specifically as enslaver has been approached by Mehran A. Nickbakht in "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery" (2006); that article approaches the pivotal passage of Tac. Ann. 1.7.1 with far more attention to detail than this essay could provide, and is thus an important basis for my argumentation.

⁴ A.J. Woodman, "Tiberius and the Taste of Power: The Year 33 in Tacitus," *The Classical Quarterly* 56 (2006), 188-189.

⁵ Suet. Tib. 61.6.

⁶ Rebecca Edwards, "Tacitus, Tiberius and Capri," *Latomus* 70 (2011), 1057.

The *princeps* as enslaver

The enslavement of free citizens and the treatment of free citizens as slaves have been associated with ‘oriental despotism’ since at least the works of Herodotus and Aischylos. A ruler who is shown humiliating or murdering his own citizens, such as Herodotus’ Cambyses,⁷ is thus to a Greek or Roman reader evocative of the tradition of Eastern tyrants. These would often be called *reges* in Roman literary canon,⁸ which further connected them to Rome’s own mythical despot-kings. Loyal writers in the early Principate were thus very careful to differentiate the concepts of *rex* and *princeps* from one another (see for example Curtius Rufus)⁹, whereas critics of single *principes*, or in the case of Tacitus the entire institution of the Principate, would draw conscious connections between the two forms of autocracy.

From the position of the Roman reader, familiar with Herodotus, the basic responsibility for the enslavement of free citizens lay not only with the despotic slaver. When Cyrus II is shown considering expanding his kingdom into a particularly rich and bounteous region, he at first declines, citing that the overflowing wealth of that region would make him and his citizens decadent and complacent, fit only to be eventually enslaved by stronger, less luxurious peoples.¹⁰ From this the idea that continuous decadence and moral decay inevitably leads to enslavement of the formerly powerful could be derived. Whosoever let his traditional mores languish would eventually descend to the level of a barbarian, whose enslavement was seen as justified from the Roman perspective.¹¹ Sallust, describing the moral development of the Republic in his *Bellum Catilinae*, follows a similar argumentative arc.¹²

⁷ Hdt. 3.34.

⁸ Tac. Ann. 2.1.

⁹ Curt. 10.9.3.

¹⁰ Hdt. 9.122.

¹¹ Wilfried Nippel, "The Construction of the ‘Other’," *Greeks and Barbarians*, ed. Thomas Harrison, (Edinburgh: University Press 2002), 291.

¹² Sall. Cat. 12.1-5.

A first indicator for this form of perceived willing enslavement in the *Annales* can be found in Tac. Ann. 1.2. The enslavement of the free citizens of Rome is accompanied by a description of the general decline of Roman morals, culminating in the loss of all societal coherence.¹³

The first true *princeps*, Augustus, is not thoroughly covered in Tacitus, but the biographer Suetonius, familiar with Tacitus, distances Augustus from the conscious enslavement of the entire *populum*. Nonetheless, he does describe at least one case in which the *princeps* treats a high-ranking citizen as a slave:

[...] et Quintum Gallium praetorem, in officio salutationis tabellas duplices veste tectas tenentem, suspicatus gladium oculere, nec quicquam statim, ne aliud inveniretur, ausus inquirere, paulo post per centuriones et milites raptum e tribunali servilem in modum torsit ac fatentem nihil iussit occidi, prius oculis eius sua manu effossis [...]

[...] when Quintus Gallius, a praetor, held some folded tablets under his robe as he was paying his respects, Augustus, suspecting that he had a sword concealed there, did not dare to make a search on the spot for fear it should turn out to be something else; but a little later he had Gallius hustled from the tribunal by some centurions and soldiers, tortured him as if he were a slave, and though he made no confession, ordered his execution, first tearing out the man's eyes with his own hand.¹⁴

This section is followed by a description of Augustus' claiming of the *tribunitia potestas*.¹⁵

Thus, the degradation of powerful citizens to slaves is directly associated with Augustus' acquisition of power.

¹³ Tac. Ann. 1.4.

¹⁴ Suet. Aug. 27.4.

¹⁵ Suet. Aug. 27.5.

The portrayal of the willing servile subordination of the aristocracy eventually begins in earnest with the ascent to power of Tiberius. This is the first transition between one *princeps* and the next within the *Annales*, and can thus be seen as exemplary for similar processes in later books. As Nickbakht mentions,¹⁶ the attention of the reader within Tac. Ann. 1.7. is suddenly drawn from the personal consequences of the death of Augustus for Tiberius towards Rome:

At Romae ruere in servitium consules, patres, eques. quanto quis inlustrior, tanto magis falsi ac festinantes, vultuque composito ne laeti excessu principis ne tristiores primordio, lacrimas gaudium, questus adulationem miscebant. Sex. Pompeius et Sex. Appuleius consules primi in verba Tiberii Caesaris iuravere [...]

Meanwhile at Rome people plunged into slavery—consuls, senators, knights. The higher a man's rank, the more eager his hypocrisy, and his looks the more carefully studied, so as neither to betray joy at the decease of one emperor nor sorrow at the rise of another, while he mingled delight and lamentations with his flattery. Sextus Pompeius and Sextus Apuleius, the consuls, were the first to swear allegiance to Tiberius Caesar [...]¹⁷

According to Matthews¹⁸, the transition from Augustus to Tiberius wasn't an unforeseeable change of paradigm. Rather, the *princeps* had spent the last years of his life ensuring that Tiberius would be able to take over his position. Tacitus uses the imagery of the “plunge into slavery” as a contrast to the previously described murder of Agrippa Postumus by Tiberius and his mother, Livia.¹⁹ Even though an autocratic tyrant has committed an unjust crime against an (admittedly flawed, but innocent) member of their own family,²⁰ he is not held accountable by a heroic defender of Republican virtue. This narrative of unpunished crime can be seen as a foil

¹⁶ Mehran A. Nickbakht, "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery: Tacitus, 'Annals' 1.7.1", *Museum Helveticum* 63 (2006); 39.

¹⁷ Tac. Ann. 1.7.

¹⁸ John Matthews, "Tacitus, Acta Senatus, and the inauguration of Tiberius," *Roman Perspectives: Studies in Political and Cultural History, from the First to the Fifth Century*, ed. John Matthews (Swansea: Classical Press of Wales 2010); 58-59.

¹⁹ Tac. Ann. 1.6.

²⁰ Tac. Ann. 1.3.

to the mythical origins of Republican values in Rome, the rape of Lucretia and the consequent dissolution of the Roman monarchy through its subjects.²¹ The latter uprising was in fact led by the ancestor of the same Marcus Iunius Brutus whose failure to defend the Republic Tacitus laments at the very beginning of the *Annales* („*Postquam Bruto et Cassio caesis nulla iam publica arma [...]*“ Tac. Ann. 1.2). Instead of a new Brutus arising to purge Tiberius’ reign, originated in violence, it is the consuls, those whose office represents the pinnacle of the *res publica*, who are the first to swear an oath on Tiberius, leading Tacitus’ *ruere in servitium*. Nickbahkt extends the verbal and thematic connections of this scene to Virgil’s depiction of Aeneas.²² In the Aeneid, Aeneas is being portrayed as a defender of *libertas*.²³ Instead of *libertas*, however, the descendants of the founders of the *res publica* are shown by Tacitus to intentionally prefer *servitium*. Seneca, according to William Turpin²⁴ an influence on Tacitus’ formulation of *exempla*, harshly condemns willing slaves who refuse to interfere with tyranny as worse than the tyrant himself, as they contribute to tyranny without even benefitting from it.²⁵

An important aspect of slavery is the “social death”, the uprooting of the slave from their previous life by taking away their previous name as well as other markers of identity, a practice common in Rome, as Bodel writes, and usually paired with maintaining fragments of the slave’s previous identity as part of a form of institutionalized liminality.²⁶ Tacitus’ Tiberius doesn’t have the members of the aristocracy die a literal social death, but he neglects mentioning their names when new consuls are being introduced to him:

²¹ Liv. 1.58-60.

²² Mehran A. Nickbakht, "Fighting for Liberty, Embracing Slavery: Tacitus, ‘Annals’ 1.7.1" (2006), 40.

²³ Verg. Aen. 8.648.

²⁴ William Turpin, "Stoic exempla, and the praecipuum munus annalium," *Classical Antiquity* 27 (2008), 368.

²⁵ Sen. Ira 3.14-15.

²⁶ John Bodel, "Death and Social Death in Ancient Rome," *On Human Bondage: After Slavery and Social Death*, eds. John Bodel & Walter Scheidel, (Chichester: Wiley Blackwell 2017), 96-97.

Modo subtractis candidatorum nominibus originem cuiusque et vitam et stipendia descripsit ut qui forent intellexeretur; aliquando ea quoque significatione subtracta candidatos hortatus ne ambitu comitia turbarent, suam ad id curam pollicitus est. Plerumque eos tantum apud se professos dissevit, quorum nomina consulibus edidisset; posse et alios profiteri, si gratiae aut meritis confiderent: speciosa verbis, re inania aut subdola, quantoque maiore libertatis imagine tegebantur, tanto eruptura ad infensius servitium.

Sometimes he kept back the names of the candidates, describing their origin, their life and military career, so that it might be understood who they were. Occasionally even these hints were withheld, and, after urging them not to disturb the elections by canvassing, he would promise his own help towards the result. Generally he declared that only those had offered themselves to him as candidates whose names he had given to the consuls, and that others might offer themselves if they had confidence in their influence or merit. A plausible profession this in words, but really unmeaning and delusive, and the greater the disguise of freedom which marked it, the more cruel the enslavement into which it was soon to plunge us.²⁷

To the strongly familial Roman aristocrats, the connection between their family name and personal accomplishments was of immense importance.²⁸ Having this connection ignored while accessing the nominally highest rank of the *res publica* was thus a severe humiliation. The utterances made by Tacitus' Tiberius about the new consuls (their place of origin and skill set) are additionally reminiscent of the information that slave merchants would provide at the market in the form of *tituli*. Tiberius is portrayed not as introducing new consuls to the Senate, but as selling them slaves, a feasible step after the "plunge into slavery" from Tac. Ann. 1.7, which also, as already mentioned, features the consuls foremost.

²⁷ Tac. Ann. 1.81.

²⁸ Helmut Rix, "Gentile," *Der Neue Pauly*, eds. Hubert Cancik, Helmut Schneider & Manfred Landfester. Accessed December 9, 2021.

The *slave as dominus*

The inversion of the enslaved aristocrat can be found in the enslaving slave, who meddles with the realm of politics that should be exclusive to the upper classes. Suetonius mentions, referring to Tacitus,²⁹ a case in which Tiberius is advised by a *coprea* (buffoon) on the manner of punishment for a treasonous aristocrat:

Annalibus suis vir consularis inseruit, frequenti quodam convivio, cui et ipse affuerit, interrogatum eum subito et clare a quodam nano astante mensae inter copreas, cur Paconius maiestatis reus tam diu viveret, statim quidem petulantiam linguae obiurgasse, ceterum post paucos dies scripsisse senatui, ut de poena Paconi quam primum statueret.

A man of consular rank writes in his annals, that at table, where he himself was present with a large company, he was suddenly asked aloud by a dwarf who stood by amongst the buffoons, why Paconius, who was under prosecution for treason, lived so long. Tiberius immediately reprimanded him for his pertness; but wrote to the senate a few days after, to proceed without delay to the punishment of Paconius.³⁰

This episode can be seen as pointing towards two grievances: on the one hand, it shows how easily manipulated Tiberius, at this time withdrawn to his pleasure island of Capri, has become. On the other hand, it inverts the order of Roman society. Instead of Senate being called into session to decide on the proper punishment for a member of Roman high society (Paconius portrays Tacitus as one of the accusers in the Silanus case),³¹ it is a slave from the bottom rungs of Roman society who gives the (potentially purely humorous, as he is a jester) advice to dispose of Paconius.

²⁹ Suetonius refers to a *vir consularis* writing about the incident in his *Annali*, which implies a Tacitean episode, likely belonging to the fifth book of the *Annales*, which has only been preserved in fragments.

³⁰ Suet. Tib. 61.6.

³¹ Tac. Ann. 3.67.

This is not the only case in which the slaves of the narratives of Suetonius or Tacitus lead to the capture or execution of influential Romans. The *Annales* repeatedly mention slaves being interrogated by Tiberius to gain incriminating evidence on their masters.³² The inflationary acquisition of slaves, seen as a sign of decadence,³³ becomes the bane of their *domini*. But not all cases of slaves turning on their masters within Tacitus' narrative are coerced; the historiographer also describes cases of slaves willingly and intentionally putting pressure on their masters by referring to Tiberius:

Exim promptum quod multorum intimis questibus tegebatur. Incedebat enim deterrimo cuique licentia impune probra et invidiam in bonos excitandi arrepta imagine Caesaris; libertique etiam ac servi, patrono vel domino cum voces, cum manus intentarent, ultro metuebantur.

Next was exposed an abuse, hitherto the subject of many a whispered complaint. The vilest wretches used a growing freedom in exciting insult and obloquy against respectable citizens, and escaped punishment by clasping some statue of the emperor. The very freedman or slave was often an actual terror to his patron or master whom he would menace by word and gesture.³⁴

The very image of the *princeps* has thus become a means of social upheaval that enables slaves and freedmen to openly question Roman societal norms. Social unrest as a consequence of misrule is a trope which is also employed by Sallust, an acknowledged influence of Tacitus.³⁵ In Sallust's works, it is the *plebs* which intends to rebel against the aristocracy in the follow-up to the Catiline Conspiracy.³⁶ Neither the slaves of Tacitus nor the plebeians of Sallust are portrayed as being justified in their rebellions. In both cases, however, their unrest is shown to be the symptom of the moral decay of the upper classes.³⁷

³² Tac. Ann. 2.30; 3.14; 3.23; 3.67.

³³ Tac. Ann. 3.53.

³⁴ Tac. Ann. 3.36.

³⁵ Tac. Ann. 3.30.

³⁶ Sall. Cat. 37.1.

³⁷ Sall.Cat. 10.1-3.

Another section which clarifies the inversion of the social order under Tiberius is the episode of the False Agrippa. In this, a slave of the previously killed Agrippa Postumus assumes the identity of his master³⁸ and prepares to march onto Rome:

Vulgabatur interim per Italiam servatum munere deum Agrippam, credebatur Romae; iamque Ostiam invectum multitudo ingens, iam in urbe clandestini coetus celebrabant, cum Tiberium anceps cura distrahere, vine militum servum suum coerceret an inanem credulitatem tempore ipso vanescere sineret: modo nihil spernendum, modo non omnia metuenda ambiguus pudoris ac metus reputabat.

It was rumoured meanwhile throughout Italy, and was believed at Rome, that Agrippa had been saved by the blessing of Heaven. Already at Ostia, where he had arrived, he was the centre of interest to a vast concourse as well as to secret gatherings in the capital, while Tiberius was distracted by the doubt whether he should crush this slave of his by military force or allow time to dissipate a silly credulity. Sometimes he thought that he must overlook nothing, sometimes that he need not be afraid of everything, his mind fluctuating between shame and terror.³⁹

The former slave of the imperial family is, even though he dies shortly thereafter, a serious threat to Tiberius. Not only is he being widely accepted as truthful and attracts followers by his reputation alone, he also appears to genuinely possess the potential to endanger Tiberius' position. Clemens' march on Rome appears as a parody of the classic hero story, archetypical for which is Herodotus' portrayal of Cyrus II:⁴⁰ The scion of the royal family, banished or condemned to death by a paranoid relative rife with tyrannical traits, returns to the capital to make claim to his rightful throne. Thus Tacitus expands on his image of Tiberius as tyrant, which as Edwards writes he also employs otherwise,⁴¹ while placing the Principate into the tradition of "oriental" Herodotean ruling dynasties.⁴² On the other hand, he also points out the weakness of the Principate, as a slave without means is capable of threatening its legitimacy

³⁸ Tac. Ann. 2.39.

³⁹ Tac. Ann. 2.40.

⁴⁰ Hdt. 1.110-112.

⁴¹ Rebecca Edwards, "Tacitus, Tiberius and Capri," *Latomus* 70 (2011), 1052-1053. Edwards refers to Tac. Ann. 6.6. specifically to explain Tacitus' depiction of Tiberius as a Platonic tragic tyrant.

⁴² R. Schmitt, "Astyages", *Encyclopaedia Iranica*, ed. Ahmad Ashraf; Accessed December 9, 2021.

through simple deception. Instead of the Senate, which under Tiberius only consists of willing slaves, it is a single actual slave who becomes the first person to attempt to topple Tiberius' power, albeit not motivated by the Republican *virtus*.

Conclusion

In his *Annales*, Tacitus adapts Sallust's means of displaying his personal grievances with the decline of the Republic by applying slavery-adjacent tropes to both the members of the Roman aristocracy and the plebs. By exchanging the roles of *dominus* and *servus* in portraying the early Principate, he guides the process already sketched out by Sallust towards its logical extreme. The social hierarchy of the Roman Republic has now been turned on its head, and the sole person to maintain their power within these upheavals is the *princeps* himself. The main responsibility for this lies not with the *princeps*, however, who is portrayed as himself being disgusted with the subordination of the enslaved senators,⁴³ but with those who are shown to not only tolerate their enslavement, but to actively plunge into it, as described in Tac. Ann. 1.7. Tacitus, having himself witnessed the turbulent Year of the Four Emperors, thus treads a path common for Flavian and post-Flavian authors of the late first and early second century AD, criticising the Principate while also coming to begrudging terms with its prolonged existence by excising himself from the senatorial class held responsible for its establishment.

A larger-scale investigation of this topic might approach Tacitus' depiction of the other *principes* of the Julio-Claudian era, as well as differences between imperial power as depicted in the *Annales* and the earlier *Histories*.

⁴³ Tac. Ann. 3.65.

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